

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

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SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Olimov Shohijahon Fozilxon-son

THE CONCEPT OF HUMAN TEMPERAMENT AND ITS SPECIFIC FEATURES

Universal
Impact Factor

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